

Free Particle Action, Resolution and Invariance

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 31, 2022

The nonrelativistic classical action of a free particle is $A = \int m v dx$ which is equivalent to time multiplied by a constant. $v = dx/dt = \text{constant}$ for free motion and infinite x resolution is assumed. One may write $v = x/t$ so that $A = \int m x dx/t$. Assuming x and t are independent which they are not in Newton's scenario yields $\partial A/\partial x = p$ where p is momentum. $A = \int m v dx$ with $v = \text{constant}$, however, leads to $\partial A/\partial x = 0$, thus there is a dilemma.

To resolve this dilemma we assume a finite unknown resolution to x , but let t have infinite resolution. Thus we write $v = \Delta x / \Delta t$ where Δx is the unknown x resolution distance as the smallest x interval distance allowed. In other words Δx does not tend to 0 so v is really an average speed within this resolution scheme. One may take a number line and mark off Δx points from the origin, but the origin may be shifted. In other words there is x invariance in this scenario which suggests a constant in this direction related to this invariance. The question is: What is this constant? One might consider either velocity or momentum (which is nonrelativistically m (rest mass) multiplied by v). One, however, wants a theory which is the same in a lab frame as in a frame moving with a constant velocity and (p, E) and (x, t) are 4-vectors in special relativity, while v is not part of a 4-vector. Thus we consider a p as being linked to an invariance in the x direction for nonrelativistic motion. Alternatively one may note that Fermat's principle associates d/dx i.e. spatial invariance in the x direction with constant momentum in this direction. Fermat's principle, however, applies to light so perhaps there is a similarity between light and a free particle with rest mass. We also suggest that spatial invariance is linked with probability i.e. the probability to be at one x versus another. Both Lagrangian and Hamiltonian theory deal largely with time derivatives. One may note that $dv/dx = 0$ for a free particle, but we are interested in a function different from v , one that yields the constant of motion associated with invariance.

We seek a function A such that $\partial A/\partial x = p$ where dx is smaller than Δx i.e. may tend to zero. The classical action written with $v = \Delta x/\Delta t$ written as x/t for simplicity with Δx and Δt being independent within the resolution ranges. In Newton's scenario the resolution ranges tend to zero so one never has x, t independence, but with fixed resolution one does. Thus $\partial A/\partial x = p$ describes the x invariance. In particular holding t constant (say $t=0$) yields $A = px$ such that the invariance in x is described by $n\pi b/p$ where b is a constant and $n=1, 2, 3 \dots$. This suggests a resolution scheme for the invariant x i.e. $\Delta x = b/p$. Then $v = \Delta x / \Delta t$.

$\partial A/\partial t = E$ which is a constant and so this also suggests an invariance in time. For $x=0$, $A = -Et$ suggesting a periodicity in t of b/E . This is independent of b/p except for the constant b which ensures that $A=0$. We focus in this note, however, on resolution b/p in the x direction and its link to b/p length units which define Δx . Thus by forcing the notion of a finite resolution in the x direction, unlike the Newtonian scenario, one is forced to think of p (momentum) as not simply being mv (nonrelativistic), but as related to an invariance in the x direction. The function defining this invariance, namely A the classical action, also serves to define Δx , the x resolution suggesting a periodic scheme in space similar to that found in light i.e. the periodicity in the electric and magnetic fields $\cos(-Et + px)$. Thus even though $A = \int m \Delta x \Delta x / \Delta t$, and $\Delta x / \Delta t = v$, one may vary Δx within the resolution range by a tiny amount dx which does tend to zero

and leave Δt unchanged. This demonstrates the invariance in the x direction of shifting Δx points which is associated with the conserved quantity momentum as shown by $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$.

These same results hold for a relativistic free particle with $A = -Et + px$, but $E = \gamma mc^2$ and $p = \gamma mv$.

Newtonian Mechanics and a Dilemma of Varying Δx Independently of t

Newtonian mechanics defines a constant velocity as $v = dx/dt$ or $v = x/t$ if both x and t have 0 as a starting point. Thus one cannot vary Δx independently of t as shown by $x = vt$. If on the other hand one has a finite resolution for x i.e. may measure x at equally Δx spaced points with t being a running variable, then $v = \Delta x / \Delta t$ at the various $n \Delta x$ points ($n=1,2,3,\dots$) with v being an average velocity. In such a case one could vary the x point associated with Δx slightly and leave Δt constant. In other words if one has an origin and the first x point is at Δx , then shifting x means shifting the origin in $x/t = v$.

This suggests a shifting of Δx points i.e. an invariance in the x direction.

To see how a dilemma arises, consider the following:

$A = \text{Classical Action for a free particle} = L t = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 t$ where $\frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \text{constant}$ ((1))

$dA/dx = 0$ ((2))

Next write $v = x/t$ or $A = \frac{1}{2} m x^2 / t$ Treating x and t as independent yields: $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ ((3))

One may note, however, that after the derivative d/dx (holding t constant is taken), x/t is set equal to v . This ensures that one shifts all x points and does not increase the width Δx .

Thus the average speed does not change and is defined by Δx denoted as x divided by Δt denoted by t , but one may change " x " holding t constant due to spatial invariance i.e. shift the Δx spaced x points without changing average velocity. Thus ((2)) does not seem to be really true in this scenario.

Probabilistic Interpretation

The Newtonian scenario is associated with finding $x(t)$ and derivatives. For a free particle $v = \text{constant}$ means $dv/dx = 0$ which suggests spatial invariance associated with the constant v or mv or any other constant multiplied by v in the nonrelativistic picture. Thus the idea of d/dx may be introduced in the Newtonian scenario, but it is applied directly to the constant itself and not to a function yielding the constant. In the Lagrangian scenario for a free particle $dL/dv = p$ and $d/dt dL/dt = 0 \rightarrow d/dt p = 0$ i.e. p is constant in time. Lagrangian theory and Hamiltonian are concerned with time derivatives and not spatial ones. The idea of spatial invariance seems to be a probabilistic one, namely that the particle has the same probability to be at one x point as another. This probabilistic interpretation becomes a little difficult then if one introduces Δx resolution because one does not know a priori what the probability distribution will be between

points separated by Dx the x resolution. Thus one is moving in a direction that is quite different from Newton's scenario. Time is disappearing from the picture in a sense except for the idea of v and one considers a spatial probabilistic picture.

Why Is Invariance in x (Shifting of Dx units) Associated with a Constant Momentum and Not Constant Velocity?

One might argue nonrelativistically that spatial invariance in the x direction should be linked to a constant namely speed not momentum. In such a case one would not necessarily choose $A = -Et + px$ because dA/dx partial = p and not v . Special relativity, however, suggests that equations in a constantly moving frame should be invariant i.e. one does not develop new physics equations in such frames. By choosing p as the x spatial invariant (as it is in Fermat's principle which is directly linked to special relativity one has $A = -Et + px$ which is a Lorentz invariant, although E and p are not nonrelativistic values anymore. We discuss this further in a section linked to special relativity. (We note that reflection from a constantly moving mirror may be solved by using Fermat's principle in the lab frame or by using Lorentz transformation and using Fermat's principle for a stationary mirror (or conservation of x momentum).

Spatial Periodicity Within the Free Particle Classical Action

The classical action function demonstrates that spatial invariance in the x direction is linked to p (momentum) and also defines the resolution in this direction. If one considers

dA/dx partial = p then for $t=0$ one has $A = px$. This takes on integer values for $x = n b/p$ where $b = \text{constant}$ and $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. In fact one may create an eigenvalue equation using:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((4))$$

which shows periodicity clearly and may be linked to probability if one takes the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$. Such a periodicity and hence resolution in Dx is not considered in the Newtonian scenario for which $Dx \rightarrow 0$. Here $Dx = b/p$ where b is an unknown constant.

Periodicity in Time

In Newton's scenario $v = x/t$ for all x/t . We argue that for a Dx resolution of b/p with a running time t , the particle has a kind of center-of-mass motion which is v , but a strange periodicity form $\exp(ipx)$ within the Dx regions.

Given $A = -Et + px$ one may also write:

$$dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((5))$$

This suggests an invariance in time as well with t and x being treated independently. Considering $-Et$, one has units of bn/E where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ and the same b constant as in b/p is

used so that $A=0$ for $x=bn/p$ and $t=bn/E$. These two resolutions are independent. b/E defines a time periodicity in time and b/p one in space, but the ratio of $b/p / (b/E)$ is not the speed of a particle with rest mass, although it is the speed for light. For a free particle with rest mass, one has to consider x and t as independent. This carries over into a bound problem with a $V(x)$. An overall energy E may be established suggesting a periodicity of b/E overall, but $\exp(ipx)$ are used to find this value of E . $\exp(-i p p/2m t)$ is not part of the solution of the bound problem with $V(x)$.

Special Relativistic Considerations

Special relativistic considerations are critical as suggested above because they establish momentum p (i.e. in the x direction) as being the constant associated with spatial invariance and not simply velocity. If there is resolution in the x direction i.e. Dx units, one has a line with marked points with Dx spacing. This may be shifted, however, i.e. there is spatial invariance and there should be a constant linked to this. Both velocity and momentum (in 1 dimension) are candidates, but (x,t) and (p,E) are 4-vectors in special relativity and speed is not. One wishes to have a theory which holds in a lab frame and a constantly moving one, thus having classical action = $.5 mvv t = -Et+px$ (nonrelativistically) already suggests a Lorentz invariant.

In fact, if one replaces $.5mvv$ with $mcc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mv$ with $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ where m is rest mass, one obtains the relativistic free action for a free particle with $v=x/t$ namely:

$$A \text{ relativistic free particle} = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv/cc} = -Et + px \quad ((6))$$

Thus $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ because there is the same invariance in x if one shifts the equally spaced Dx units. Furthermore for $t=0$ $A=px$ so that one has natural b/p spacings in x where b is a constant. Similarly $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ and there are natural time units of b/E although time and x are again independent.

To see how t and x are independent one may note that the nonrelativistic limit of ((6)) follows from:

$$P \text{ relativistic} \rightarrow p \text{ nonrelativistic for } v \ll c \quad \text{and} \quad E \text{ relativistic} \rightarrow m_0 c^2 + .5mvv \text{ for } v \ll c$$

$$\text{Thus } -Et+px \text{ relativistic} = m_0 c^2 t + (-Et+px) \text{ nonrelativistic} \quad ((7))$$

In other words there is an extra $m_0 c^2 t$ piece in the relativistic equation, but it has nothing to do with dynamics because m is rest mass and is dropped in the nonrelativistic scenario i.e. $m_0 c^2$ does not affect the Lagrangian equation $d/dt dL/dv \text{ (partial)} - dL/dx = 0$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although we have considered the idea of wavelength and frequency following from $-Et+px$ for a free particle before we treated x and t in this expression as independent a priori. Newton's scenario keeps x and t linked through $x=vt$. In the Action = $-Et+px$ scenario one

also treats $x/t=v$, but only after taking derivatives. In this note we wish to find an explanation for treating x and t independently and for associating d/dx a mathematical space shift operator with momentum. We argue that if one introduces a resolution Dx for x then has a line with points separated by Dx . These points may be shifted i.e. there is spatial invariance in the problem and it should be associated with a constant. Mathematically one may take d/dx of an expression with x and then apply $x/t=v$ to show that Dx is not being changed, but shifted.

We suggest that this constant should be either v or momentum. The latter, however, is part of a 4-vector in special relativity while v is not and we wish to have a Lorentz invariant theory so we choose p . We next ask: What function A demonstrates that spatial invariance yields p ? For $t=0$ we expect $A = px$. One may see that the classical action for a free particle with $v=x/t$ leads both nonrelativistically and relativistically to $A = -Et+px$ (although E and p have different definitions). Thus we suggest that A is such a function. Also dA/dx being associated with px suggests a special length or wavelength $1/p$ which may be associated with Dx . An eigenvalue equation is: $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. Thus we suggest that one way to look at a free particle is to assume a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ as probabilistically describing space with a kind of center of mass motion $s=$ such that $v=x/t$. Alternatively one may consider dA/dt partial in the action as indicating a frequency proportional to $1/E$ for the independent variable time.